

-ABSTRACT.

We defined in [3] the perfect r-narcissistic numbers, or rppdi, which are a natural extension of the classic ppdi or Armstrong number of the first kind ([1]). We have shown that the set of these rppdi is finite and we have given the list of the first 15 rppdi greater than 1 in decimal base ([4], [OEIS2]).

Let us now consider the ppdi and the rppdi in any base b; we will thus define two distinct families (ppdib, ppdi0) on the one hand and (rppdib, rppdi0) on the other hand, associated with any base b other than the decimal base.

We will treat here the cases of bases from 3 to 9 (base 2 only has the trivial solution 1 and base 10 corresponds to the classic ppdi and rppdi) without taking into account the common trivial solution 1.

-INTRODUCTION -

For a k-digit number n, the function $S_p(n)$ will express the sum of the powers $p \geq 1$ of all the digits of n:
 $n = \sum_{i=1}^{i=k} a_i 10^{k-i}$, $a_1 > 0$, $S_p(n) = \sum_{i=1}^{i=k} a_i^p$, $p \geq 1$.

To move on to rppdi, we apply S_p , not to n (as for ppdi), but to a power r (> 1) of n.

Recall that a perfect r-narcissistic number or rppdi ([3], [4]) is an integer n (> 1) with p digits whose power r > 1 (r = 1 corresponding to the classic ppdi) is such that the sum of the powers p of all its digits $S_p(n^r)$ is equal to the number n.

While a p-digit ppdi is a solution of $n = S_p(n)$, a p-digit rppdi is a solution of $n = S_p(n^r)$ for $r > 1$.

An rppdi is therefore a p-digit fixed point of the transformation S_p^r

$$(1) \quad n \rightarrow S_p^r(n) = S_p(n^r), r > 1,$$

a ppdi being a fixed point with p digits of (1) but with $r = 1$.

In any base b ($2 < b < 10$), n becomes n_b and we apply the transformation S_p^r to n_b ; we then look for fixed points of: $n = S_p^r(n_b)$, for $r = 1$ (ppdi) or $r > 1$ (rppdi).

With p = number of digits of n_b , then denoted p_b , we obtain the ppdi in base b or ppdib, and the rppdi in base b or rppdib; in this case it is the number n_b which has p digits.

With p = number of digits of n, then denoted p_0 , we obtain fixed points of S_p^r which we will respectively call ppdi0 ($r = 1$) and rppdi0 ($r > 1$); in this case it is the number n which has p digits.

Let us add that for ppdi, only ppdib are considered by the authors ([2], [OEIS1]).

The pleasant character of the transformations S_p^r ([3], [4]) leads to the finiteness of the sets of integers, {ppdib}, {ppdi0} of a on the other hand, {rppdib}, {rppdi0} on the other hand; the set, also finite ([4]), of all the fixed points of the pleasant transformation S_p^r , contains the first two for $r = 1$ and the last two for $r > 1$.

For finiteness, we can also draw inspiration from the general demonstration of [5], and frame such numbers n with k digits in base b by (since $n^r < 10^{kr}$):

$$(2) \quad b^{k-1} < n < rk(b-1)^k, \text{ with } r = 1 \text{ for ppdi and } r > 1 \text{ for rppdi,}$$

the lower limit being the smallest k-digit number, the upper limit being the image by S_k^r of the largest.

We can then easily show that for all b, and all r, there exists a $k^*(b, r)$ such that, in (2), the lower limit is strictly greater than the upper limit; there will therefore be no solution for $k \geq k^*(b, r)$, which ensures the finite nature of all of these numbers for any base (and any finite r).

For example, for rppdib, $k^*(10,1) = 61$, $k^*(10,2) = 69$, ..., $k^*(10,6) = 81$, $k^*(9,1) = 53$, $k^*(9,2) = 60$, $k^*(9,3) = 64$, ..., $k^*(8,2) = 51$, $k^*(8,4) = 57$, ...

All ppdi as well as all rppdi are finite in number in all bases and the corresponding definition intervals are $[1, 10^{k^*(b,r)-1}[$, $b > 2$, $r \geq 1$.

The integers common to the two sets {ppdib}, {ppdi0} respectively {rppdib}, {rppdi0}, are n which have exactly the same number of digits in decimal base and in the base b concerned.

To be more readable we will give all our results by expressing them in decimal base.

-1 - PPDIs

The ppdi in decimal base ([2]) and in any base in the form of ppdib ([2], [OEIS1]) are well listed in the literature, but not in the version of ppdi0.

Naturally, in decimal base, the ppdib and the ppdi0 are identified with the well-known ppdi: we know

([1]) that there are 88 including: 1, ..., 9, 153, 370, 371, ..., 115.132.219.018.763.992.565.095.597.973.971.522.401.

To simplify the results concerning ppdib, ppdi0 in base b, we do not cite or count trivial solutions 1, 2, ..., b-1.

-1 - 1 - The PPDIB

Here $p = p_b$.

This choice is the one adopted in [2] as in [OEIS1].

In $[2, 10^9]$, the results, written in base 10, provide 96 solutions.

b = 3 has 3 solutions: 5, 8, 17.

b = 4 has 8 solutions: 28, 29, 35, 43, 55, 62, 83, 243.

b = 5 has 12 solutions: 13, 18, 28, 118, 289, 353, 419, 4.890, 4.891, 9.113, 1.874.374, 338.749.352.

b = 6 has 12 solutions: 99, 190, 2.292, 2.293, 2.324, 3.432, 3.433, 6.197, 36.140, 269.458, 391.907, 10067135.

b = 7 has 26 solutions: 10, 25, 32, 45, 133, 134, 152, 250, 3.190, 3.222, 3.612, 3.613, 4.183, 9.286, 35.411, 191.334, 193.393, 376.889, 535.069, 794.376, 8.094.840, 10.883.814, 16.219.922, 20.496.270, 32.469.576, 34.403.018.

b = 8 has 21 solutions: 20, 52, 92, 133, 307, 432, 433, 16.819, 17.864, 17.865, 24.583, 25.639, 212.419, 906.298, 906.426, 938.811, 1.122.179, 2.087.646, 3.821.955, 13.606.405, 40.695.508.

b = 9 has 14 solutions: 41, 50, 126, 127, 468, 469, 1.824, 8.052, 8.295, 9.857, 1.198.372, 3.357.009, 3.357.010, 6.287.267.

Example: in base 6, we have $99 = 243_6$, $p = 3$, $S_3(243) = 2^3 + 4^3 + 3^3 = 99$.

1- 2 - The PPDIO

Here $p = p_0$.

This choice is, to our knowledge, not used, but it is nonetheless also natural since it is associated with the number of digits of the initial n (and not of the transformed n_b). We obtain in our search interval, 34 solutions such that n and n_b have the same length, and therefore common to the two sets {ppdib}, {ppdi0}.

In $[2, 10^9]$, the results, written in base 10, provide 43 solutions.

b = 3 has 0 solution.

b = 4 has 0 solution.

b = 5 has 3 solutions: 13, 18, 118.

b = 6 has 2 solutions: 190, 251.

b = 7 has 8 solutions: 10, 25, 32, 45, 133, 134, 152, 250.

b = 8 has 15 solutions: 20, 52, 133, 307, 432, 433, 16.819, 17.864, 17.865, 24.583, 25.639, 212.419, 1.122.179, 2.087.646, 13.606.405.

b = 9 has 15 solutions: 41, 50, 126, 127, 468, 469, 1.824, 65.538, 65.539, 1.198.372, 3.357.009, 3.357.010, 5.300.099, 156.608.073, 156.608.074.

Example: in base 6, we have $251 = 1055_6$, $p = 3$, $S_3(1055) = 1^3 + 5^3 + 5^3 = 251$.

Let us observe that in $[2, 10^9]$ there are 96 ppdib for 43 ppdi0 ...

Let us state a property common to ppdib and ppdi0 in any base b.

- PROPERTY 1

For any base b, if a fixed point m of $S_p(n_b)$, with $p = p_b$ or p_0 , is a multiple of b, then $m + 1$ is also the fixed point of this application.

Indeed, if $m = 0(b)$, m_b ends with a 0 (in $m_b = \sum_{i=1}^{i=p} a_i b^{p-i}$ we will have $a_p = 0$), and if m is a solution, $m + 1$ is also a solution since a_p will become equal to 1 and will remain so at any power.

Examples: 370, 371 in base 10 for ppdi; 28, 29 in base 4 for ppdib; 156.608.073, 156.608.074 in base 9 for ppdi0, ...

-2 - RPPDI

In ([3], [4]), the rppdi were defined and the list ([OEI2]) of the first 15 rppdi greater than 1 in decimal base was given (we write 8(3) for solution 8 with $r = 3$):

7(4), 8(3), 9(2);

180(6), 205(2);

38.998(2), 45.994(2), 89.080(2);

726.191(2);

5.540.343(3), 7.491.889(2), 8.690.141(3);

167.535.050(3), 749.387.107(4);
9.945.245.922(3).

We will determine here the representatives in base b ($2 < b < 10$) for the two choices of p .
We will observe that in $[2, 10^9]$ there are 17 rppdib for 47 rppdi0 ...

-2 - 1 - The RPPDIB

With $p = p_b$, the results, written in base 10, give 17 solutions in $[2, 10^9]$:

(solution 10 for $r = 2$ will be noted 10(2))

$b = 3$ has 1 solution: 10(2)

$b = 4$ has 0 solution

$b = 5$ has 1 solution: 6(2)

$b = 6$ has 1 solution: 30(3)

$b = 7$ has 2 solutions: 33(2);

56(3)

$b = 8$ has 6 solutions: 16(2), 41(2), 129(2), 432(2), 9.808(2);

7(4)

$b = 9$ has 6 solutions: 42(2), 684(2), 52.777(2);

8(3);

7(4), 468(4)

Example: $9.808 = 23.120_8$, $p = 5$, $r = 2$, $23.120^2 = 534.534.400$, $S_5(534.534.400) = 5^5 + 3^5 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 3^5 + 4^5 + 4^5 = 9.808$.

-2 - 2 - The RPPDI0

With $p = p_0$, the results, written in base 10, give 47 solutions in $[2, 10^9]$:

$b = 3$ has 5 solutions: 4(2), 33(2), 95(2), 5.121(2);

7294(3)

$b = 4$ has 20 solutions:

9(2), 33(2), 129(2), 480(2), 640(2), 736(2), 34.816(2), 69.666(2), 2.129.920(2), 4.259.970(2),
134.742.016(2), 269.484.546(2), 335.028.856(2);

8(3), 20(3), 512(3), 32.768(3), 2.097.152(3), 134.217.728(3);

8(9).

$b = 5$ has 1 solution: 81.748(4)

$b = 6$ has 2 solutions: 90.646(2);

30(3)

$b = 7$ has 5 solutions: 9(2), 33(2), 9.667(2), 68.266(2);

8(3)

$b = 8$ has 6 solutions: 16(2), 41(2), 129(2), 432(2);

977.797(3);

7(4)

$b = 9$ has 8 solutions: 42(2), 684(2), 9.778(2), 52.777(2), 8.767.684(2);

8(3);

7(4), 468(4).

Example: $9667 = 40.120_7$, $p = 4$, $r = 2$, $40.120^2 = 1.609.614.400$, $S_4(1.609.614.400) = 1^4 + 6^4 + 9^4 + 6^4 + 1^4 + 4^4 + 4^4 = 9.667$.

As for the ppdi, the solutions n of the same length as the associated n_b , are common to the two sets $\{\text{rppdib}\}$, $\{\text{rppdi0}\}$, there are 13 in our search interval.

The results obtained with our two choices allow us to observe some pathologies.

- PROPERTY 2

1) Among the rppdi0, there exists a solution n with two different r for $b = 4$: 8(3) and 8(9) (this answers a question implicitly asked in [5] concerning the rppdi in decimal base and the uniqueness of the r of a solution).

2) Among the rppdi0, we have 3 times the solution 33(2): in bases 3, 4 and 7.

3) For the base $b = 4$, there is no solution of type rppdib but 20 solutions of type rppdi0 in the search interval $[2, 10^9]$.

Base 4 appears to be the most prolific for rppdi0.

- 4) The solution $n = 8$ appears 4 times in the $rppdi0$ ($2 < b < 10$) including 3 times with $r = 3$: $8(3)$ and $8(9)$ for $b = 4$; $8(3)$ for $b = 7$; $8(3)$ for $b = 9$.
- 5) Among the $rppdib$ and $rppdi0$, the solution $n = 7$ appears twice: with $b = 8$ and $b = 9$ and each time with $r = 4$.
- 6) The various properties of 8:
8 is equal to the sum of the digits of its cube (512).
8 is equal to the sum of the digits of the cube of its expression in base 4 (which is 8.000).
8 is equal to the sum of the digits of the power of 9 of its expression in base 4 (which is $512 \cdot 10^9$).
8 is equal to the sum of the digits of the power of 3 of its expression in base 7 (which is 1.331).

-CONCLUSION -

After the finite set of $\{rppdi\}$ ([3], [4], [5], [OEIS2]) which has, in decimal base, 15 representatives in $[2, 10^{10}]$, we have defined three new finite sets of narcissistic numbers in bases 3 to 9, $\{ppdi0\}$, $\{rppdib\}$ and $\{rppdi0\}$. In the interval $[2, 10^9]$, they have, respectively, 43, 17 and 47 elements that we have determined.

(*) Honorary Professor at the University of Toulouse, France; Webmaster of the site SAYRAC, E-mail: renelouis.clerc@free.fr.

- REFERENCES -

- [1] Armstrong numbers of the first kind or $ppdi$, [OEIS A005188](https://oeis.org/A005188).
- [2] O.Cira, F.Smarandache, Various arithmetic functions and their applications, PONS asbl, Bruxelles, 2016.
- [3] R.L.Clerc, Les transformations agréables et une nouvelle classe de nombres narcissiques parfaits, p.1-17, (zenodo.org/records/19004709, 2026), 2022.
- [4] R.L.Clerc, The perfect r -narcissistic numbers, p.1-2, (zenodo.org/records/19030196, 2026), 2023.
- [5] R.L.Clerc, Quelques nombres de Niven-Harshad particuliers, p.1-18, (zenodo.org/records/19018760, 2026), 2023.
- [OEIS1] Armstrong numbers of the first kind in base 9, [OEIS A010353](https://oeis.org/A010353), N.J.A. Sloane, J.Myers; with references to bases 4 to 16, 2009.
- [OEIS2] R -narcissistic numbers ($rppdi$), [OEIS A364601](https://oeis.org/A364601), R.L.Clerc, 2023.